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Assessment of Thermal Comfort in Studios of The Department of Architecture, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Yelwa Campus

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Abstract

One of the main functions of a building is to protect the occupants against harsh outdoor climate and to provide a comfortable and healthy indoor environment for the occupants (students and teachers) that would impact on their productivity and performance. Thermal comfort is one of the parameters that impact on the satisfaction of the occupants of a building. In order to evaluate their thermal conditions during the student's instructional time, this study was conducted. This paper investigated the level of thermal comfort in Architecture studio Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi such that design should focus on approach, techniques and processes that will improve efficiency of energy in buildings without disregarding user comfort. The study employs adaptive assessment which involves questionnaire survey which were employed during the study. All the Data was collected during the month of March and April of the year 2023. The study indicates all respondents (100%) agreed that high level windows should be able to be opened rather than fixed. 80% of respondents concur that fixed window glazing at particular building locations or heights has an impact on their illumination and comfort. The study's conclusion states that lowering conduction heat transfer, infiltration, solar gain, and ventilation can improve thermal comfort both within and outside the studio building.

Keywords: Architecture, Buildings, Indoor Environment, Outdoor climate and Thermal Comfort.

1. Introduction

The need for thermal comfort in institutional building has been a major concern in the assessment of design to achieve a significant design that would be conducive for occupants. Thermal comfort has to be in consideration right from the conceptual stage of a building in order to harmonize its characteristics with the climatic design objectives of the building towards health and thermal comfort. One of the basic requirements of this environment is to maintain thermal conditions comfortable for occupants as these have a direct effect on health, productivity and morale (ASHRAE Standard 55). Abiodun (2014). defines thermal comfort as the "state of the mind that expresses satisfaction with the surrounding environment". According to (Health and Safety Executive) the term 'thermal comfort' describes a person's state of mind in terms of whether he/she feels too hot or too cold.

Standards such as ASHRAE Standard 55 and ISO Standard 7730 have been the basis in the determination of thermal comfort by most practitioners and researchers (ISO Standard 7730).

Nonetheless, people in different climatic zones feel comfortable at different indoor air temperatures: a situation which can vary considerably from that of the world standards. The environmental factors affecting thermal comfort conditions are: (1) dry bulb temperature, (2) mean radiant temperature, (3) relative humidity and (4) air velocity) and two personal (clothing-insulation and physical activity) parameters (ISO Standard 7730). The definition of air temperature given by Mora and Bean (2018) is "the temperature of the air surrounding the person." The most important factor in determining whether someone would feel heat stress is the air temperature, which is also the most common indicator of thermal comfort. The idea that prompted this research work evolved as a result of an observation related to human health and comfort in institutional buildings of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University architectural studio during hot discomfort period. There is a rampant case of cerebra-spinal meningitis experienced as a result of

poor air movement into buildings during the hot period due to small openings and lack of cross ventilation (Kama, 2023). According to Kama (2023), the year with the most cases (215) was recorded in 2016 and the fewest cases (58, or 3.2%), was 2003. The most cases (415) were reported in the month of April, while the fewest (27) were reported in the month of December. The sickness first becomes more prevalent in January and reaches its heights in March, April, and May, when the temperature is also higher. The goal of managing comfort in institutional buildings is to find the best possible air quality inside of institutional buildings for practical reasons. This helps significantly to consider the design, right from the conceptual stage of a building in order to avoid the unforeseen mistakes. This study will be helpful to architectural designers. The study is expected to produce possible means of checking or overcoming comfort in regard to the occupants' health, discomfort ability by solving them all. The main objective is an assessment of thermal comfort in the studios of the department of architecture, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Yelwa campus while the specific objectives include to investigate the occupant degree of comfort inside and around the building, determining the adequacy of wind sensation during the hot periods of March-April, in afternoon and evening times and to identify possible and promising ways to improve thermal comfort in and around the building's environment.

2. Literature Review

Natural Ventilation in Institutional Buildings

Ventilation is the process of exchanging or removing air to maintain a high level of indoor air quality and to control humidity and temperature. Ventilation provides fresh air to cool the body, removes accumulated harmful vapours and contaminants, and removes heat generated by convection in a workspace. The purpose of classroom ventilation is to create a comfortable indoor environment, and classrooms may be naturally ventilated, mechanically ventilated, or have mixed mode ventilation. Mechanically ventilated spaces are those in which motor-powered fans and turbines are utilized to circulate air. According to Muhammad (2021), mixed mode ventilation, also known as hybrid ventilation, is a combination of natural ventilation (from operable windows) and mechanical system. This form of

ventilation is prevalent in Nigeria, where naturally ventilated buildings have no mechanical ventilation systems.

Naturally ventilated spaces refer to the passage of outdoor air into an interior space without the use of mechanical systems, relying instead solely on pressure differences caused by natural forces. When wind travels around a building, both the windward and leeward areas experience a pressure decrease. The building's apertures will utilize the dynamic pressure decrease to draw air through these openings, removing heat and pollutants from the interior space. Beccali, Strazzeri, Germanà, Melluso and Galatioto (2018) found that a natural ventilation system increases thermal comfort indoors while decreasing energy consumption by 31.6% compared to a conventional mechanical ventilation system. The condition of university facilities was found to be a critical factor contributing to uncomfortable thermal condition in higher educational institutions as similarly observed in the area of study. There is a need therefore, to find out properties and values of building envelope materials used in construction with their various technical characteristics. According to Olanipekun, Olugboyega and Ojelabi (2017), thermal comfort and energy consumption standards are not defined in Nigeria building codes and there is little research on how, and what extent the performance of the buildings influence the academic performance of students and users of these buildings. Different building indoor environmental performance indicators and criteria around the world have been developed and yet, most seem incomplete and not useful in the study area. The use of natural ventilation to enhance evaporative and convective cooling of occupants is one strategy for buildings in the humid tropics, which are characterised by high temperature and relative humidity and low wind velocity (Amasuomo & Amasuomo, 2016).

Thermal Comfort

Thermal comfort is an essential component in the design and operation of buildings because it has a direct influence on the levels of contentment, wellness, and productivity that occupants experience inside interior spaces. It is a condition in which inhabitants do not experience feelings of being too hot or underlay cold, but rather feel as though they are in a state of thermal balance. Maintaining the appropriate air temperature, humidity, air movement, and radiant heat exchange are all necessary components to achieve ideal

thermal comfort. Thermal comfort is described as a "condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment" by the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) (ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55-2013, 2013). ASHRAE's definition of thermal comfort is about a person's psychological frame of mind, whether the person feels neither 'too hot nor too cold' or thermally neutral given that the person is healthy and wears a normal quantity of clothing at the time of evaluation. Thermal conditions refer to the ambient temperature, humidity and air flow rate in a workplace as well as thermal radiation. These physical conditions have an effect on how a worker is subjected to strain in their work.

Factors that Influence Indoor Thermal Comfort Conditions

The evaluation of the thermal comfort of the human body is connected to aspects of the environment, aspects of the human organism, and aspects of the clothes. To create situations that the vast majority of people will regard as pleasant, it is necessary to take into account all of the components that go into creating such conditions (Lança, Coelho, & Viegas, 2019). The temperature of the air, the velocity at which the air is moving, the radiant temperature, and the relative humidity are all measurable parameters that impact thermal comfort. Activity level and the insulation provided by clothes are two of the personal elements that determine thermal comfort.

The temperature of the air, the relative humidity of the air, the speed of the air, and the radiant temperature are all environmental parameters. The pace of one's metabolism, the kind of activities one engages in, one's age, gender, and weight are among the aspects that influence the human body. The thermal resistance of the clothes, the structure of the material, the number of layers, and other aspects are all important considerations. These elements have a variety of implications on the occupants' ability to maintain a comfortable temperature. A person's age, health, the weather, the time of year, and their expectations are among the other things that might influence their internal temperature balance. There is a correlation between these parameters that determines the thermal comfort zone, and there are several suggested values in standards that may be utilised for measurements (Tammy & Oweikeye, 2016). According to Waziri, Usman & Enaburekhan (2015). in their study demonstrate that the temperature and relative humidity during the hot and dry season were higher than the standard.

The Temperature Humidity Index according to Windchill Metrology in the United States is the combination of temperature and humidity that is a measure of the degree of discomfort experienced by an individual usually in warm weather. The index is essentially an effective temperature based on air temperature and humidity. It equals 15 plus 0.4 times the sum of simultaneous readings of the dry and wet bulb temperatures. Based on the measurement so far in the study area the dry bulb temperature is 95°F (35°C) and wet bulb is 50°F (10°C)

The discomfort index is hence calculated as $15 + 0.4(145) = 73^\circ\text{F}$ (1)

Most humans are comfortable when the index is less than 71°F. from equation 1 it is recommended that even if the discomfort sensation is not obvious, adequate protection measures should be taken hence there is an urgent need to seek cooler internal environment by sensible and passive design methods to cool the lecture spaces. All studio surveyed rely on ceiling fan and AC for cooling. Notwithstanding the use of ACs and fans, indoor temperatures in all buildings during the survey were still high ranging from about 30 - 42°C. This is due to obvious air leakages from open windows which is not supposed to function with open fenestration. User occupant sensitisation is key even with the best design consideration followed in generating these lecture spaces. There is need for a continuous awareness so as to guide the operationalisation of these lecture spaces.

Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)

According to Fanger (1970); Jay et. Al (2021) is the one who developed the indexes known as the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) and the Predicted People Dissatisfied (PPD). Both are only variations of the same evaluation instrument, but they are presented in a different format. While the ASHRAE PMV thermal scale of ideal acceptability goes from -0.5 to +0.5, the ISO Standard of acceptability ranges from cold (-1) to hot (+3), with just 10% of people being unhappy with the range. According to Fanger's research from 1970, the percentage of unsatisfied tenants in a building drop below 20% when the PMV value of the building's thermal environment is between -0.85 and +0.85. Up to this point, the PMV has been accepted as a building environment evaluation index by international standards such as ISO 7730, ASHRAE Standard 55, and CEN 15251. The application of the operational temperature, human traits and the conditions of the interior environment both have an impact on

thermal comfort. The temperature of the air, the mean radiant temperature, the relative humidity, and the velocity of the air are the indoor parameters. The effect that these factors have on the thermal comfort of building occupants is affected by the local climate as well as by the building's exterior.

Discussion of The PMV Scale and Its Interpretation in Relation to Thermal Comfort Assessment

Research based on their individual studies such as Arif, Katafygiotou, Mazroei, Kaushik, & Elsarrag (2016) and Munonye & Ji (2018) have shown that thermal comfort consistently came as the number one complaint by building occupants over other indoor environmental attributes such as air cleanliness, odour, and noise, particularly in the tropics. The surplus heat that is created within the human body because of metabolism must be transmitted into the surrounding environment so that the temperature of the core of the body can remain stable and this allows for thermal comfort. A person needs to maintain a steady body temperature in order to be able to radiate heat from their metabolism into the environment. 2020 (Charles, 2020). According to Charles (2020), the heat loss is demonstrated by three types: radiation (45%), convection (35%) and evaporation (20%) pointed out the heat transfer between a human body and the environment. The interplay between improved IEQ and occupants' health and productivity benefits has been identified in numerous studies (Spengler *et al.*, 2001; Sharaidin *et al.*, 2012; GBCA 2013b), however, conventional higher education buildings in Nigeria are generally only designed to comply with a minimum standard in building codes. This means most educational buildings are constructed with little provision in their spaces an acceptable level of comfort for the occupants that are not always energy efficient (GBCA, 2013b).

The ability of the building envelope like walls and windows to decrease heat gain into the building can be explained in terms of their thermal properties. This component should be able to control internal environmental factors to enhance comfort. According Bello, Allu-Kangkum, and Nimlyat (2021) existing building components most often not properly conceived in the design stage have limited measures for improving thermal comfort and energy consumption of building occupants. Bello, Allu-Kangkum, and Nimlyat (2021) also affirmed in their studies that from the results of analysis of case studies confirmed thermal discomfort in Higher Educational buildings. There is urgent need

to improve comfort level in and reduce energy demand due to too much reliance on mechanical cooling systems.

3. Research Methodology

The study was carried out using quantitative survey method. The questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was collected during the dry season of March-April, 2023 in the afternoons at 12 noon and evening times at 4pm which are characterised to be hot hours. The rationale behind the selection of April and March pertains to the variability of temperature patterns, which is contingent upon the prevailing climatic conditions and geographical location. The sample population comprise the individuals who occupy the premises. This could encompass a variety of individuals, such as employees, students, educators, or any other frequent occupants of the premises which are over four thousand individuals as obtained from the records of the Faculty of Environmental Technology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University. According to Yemane's (1990) as adopted by Singh & Masuku, (2014) sample determining formula. The researcher will use a 95% confident level and 5% error. This implies that the total sample size is

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(E)^2} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where n = required sample
 N = Total Population
 E = Error (The level of precision)

$$n = 4,000\{1 + 4,000 \times 0.052\}$$

$$n = 4,000\{1 + 4,000 \times 0.0025\}$$

$$n = 4,000\{1 + 10\} \quad n = 4,00011$$

$$n = 363.63636\dots \quad n \sim 364$$

Based on the calculations above, the estimated sample size is 364.

The sample of the study is 364.

The procedure adopted for data collection was the stratified random sampling whereby copies of the questionnaires were administered and a checklist for physical observation. The questionnaire had two sections containing eleven (11) questions. Section A: personal data contained four questions and section B: adequate wind sensation during the hot

periods of March-April, in afternoon and evening times, contained seven questions. Furthermore, alterations in weather patterns and the occurrence of climate change can introduce additional fluctuations and divergences from customary temperature patterns. Hence, this is the reason behind the choice of those particular months.

Data Analysis Instrument and Procedure

The data analysis instrument used in this research is the descriptive statistical method of tabulation and finding of percentage. The data analysis procedure for this study is based on the information obtained from field observation and questionnaires administration. This is done by editing the response and presenting them for visual comprehension. For the purpose of this research work descriptive statistic was used using SPSS V25, the following results were obtained 450 questionnaires were distributed 403 were returned while 24 were found with missing information.

Area of study

The Architecture studio, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Bauchi is located within the university campus (Yelwa Campus). Bauchi, usually referred to as Bauchi

State to distinguish it from the city of Bauchi. Bauchi State is located in north-eastern Nigeria (See Figure 1). It occupies a total land area of 49,119 km² (18,965 sq mi), representing about 5.3% of Nigeria's total land mass and is located between latitudes 9° 3' and 12° 3' north and longitudes 8° 50' and 11° east. The State is bordered by seven States, Kano and Jigawa to the north, Taraba and Plateau to the south, Gombe and Yobe to the east and Kaduna to the west. The climate for Bauchi is hot and dry for most period of the year. The mean temperature is about 35.3 °C. The highest temperature of about 40 °C is normally experienced in April, while minimum temperature of about 13 °C is recorded in January. Bauchi exhibits a remarkably high annual range of mean monthly temperature. Its capital is Bauchi city which is located in Bauchi Local Government Area of the State, a part of the traditional Bauchi Emirate (See Figure 2). It is located on the northern edge of the Jos Plateau, at an elevation of 616 m. The city has a population of 316,173 persons (medianigeria.com, 2022). Bauchi is known as an education centre within the North-East Region of Nigeria. The hot dry climate of this part of the country necessitated this study.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing Bauchi State
Source: nationsonline.org (2022)

This building is one amongst other intervention building by TetFund to the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. The project was aimed at providing a better comfortable Studio space for students compared to existing spaces which were just make shift conversion to serve as studio spaces.

The functional spaces in the building are the entrance porch, toilets, studio Halls, offices and passages/walkways. Figure 3-6 shows a view of the building as captured during data collection and

Figure 2: Map of Bauchi State (Bauchi metropolis is encircled)
Source: nigeriazipcodes.com (2021)

Figure 7 shows the floor plan with total floor area of 1868 square meter as collected from the physical planning unit of the institution.

Building elements

The external and internal walls of the building were constructed with 9 inches hollow sandcrete block. Both the external and internal walls were rendered using sand/cement plaster. The external walls were painted with beige/light brown colour emulsion paint. All windows were single-glazed combination

of fixed light, Projected and aluminium sliding windows. The windows were fitted with reinforced concrete vertical shading device with fins of about 200mm as shown earlier in figures 3-7. The windows were also fixed with aluminium burglar-proof to enhance the security of the building from burglars and thieves.

The ceiling was constructed using suspended acoustic ceiling boards. The ceiling height from the floor surface was 5.2m. This measurement was taken during the survey of the building. The uninsulated slightly barrel roof construction was covered with cream coloured corrugated Long Span Aluminum roofing sheets. The roof has no roof vent but had eave vent for convection airflow, which can help to cool interior spaces. Some lessons learnt from case study in terms of design, energy efficiency and thermal comfort include:

i. Though the building was not designed with in-depth knowledge of energy efficiency as they were no policy in this regard when the building was constructed, nevertheless, the building has some elements that can enhance energy efficiency and thermal comfort. The use of projected windows gives maximum

opening on the external walls for ventilation which aid thermal comfort in the building. The use of shading devices on the window was a good attempt at preventing the effect of direct sun through the window glazing and internal surfaces but this were not again properly distributed.

ii. Buildings in the study area requires large openings especially on external wall to improve ventilation in interior spaces. As asserted by Harvey (2009) sufficient number of openings is required to produce airflow for passive cooling. Hence, maintaining a single window type may be more suitable than combination of window types which was used in the building.

iii. The use of burglar-proof on windows reduces the amount of airflow into the building. Therefore, there may be need to increase the sizes of windows to cover for this reduction.

iv. There are visibly no adequate trees and vegetation to provide shading that will enhance cooling around and within the building

Figure 3: Picture showing Approach view of Department of Architecture Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Yelwa Campus Bauchi State

Source: Author's fieldwork (2023)

Figure 4: Picture showing Rear view of Department of Architecture Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Yelwa Campus Bauchi State

Source: Author's fieldwork (2023)

Figure 5: Picture showing Architecture Studio in the Department of Architecture Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Yelwa Campus Bauchi State

Source: Author's fieldwork (2023)

Figure 6: Picture showing Hallway in the Department of Architecture Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Yelwa Campus Bauchi State

Source: Author's fieldwork (2023)

Figure 7: Picture showing Floor Plan Layout in the Department of Architecture Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Yelwa Campus Bauchi State

Source: Author's fieldwork (2023)

4. Results

How does natural ventilation affect comfort in the study area?

Table 1: Comfort and natural ventilation

S/N	Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Rank
1.	Human comfort and natural ventilation	4.243	1.963	1 st
2.	Natural ventilation for indoor air quality	4.092	1.944	2 nd
3.	Natural ventilation for passive cooling	3.904	0.803	3 rd
4.	Natural ventilation for cooling	3.451	1.622	4 th
5.	Design considerations	2.834	0.824	5 th
6.	Comfort ventilation and air movement	2.212	0.803	6 th

Source: Field Work (2023)

Table 1 shows the comfort and natural ventilation result of respondents in the study area which reveals human comfort and natural ventilation with mean score of 4.2431 followed by natural ventilation for indoor air quality with mean score of 4.0923.

Natural ventilation for passive cooling with mean score of 3.9042 and natural ventilation for cooling with the mean score of 3.4513 respectively. Air flow in the immediate environment has a significant impact on human thermal comfort and this impact has been investigated for almost a century.

What are the problems associated with thermal comfort in the study area?

Table 2: Problems associated with thermal comfort

S/N	Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Rank
1.	Solar radiation and temperature and clouds	4.212	1.796	1 st
2.	Humidity design consideration	3.804	1.624	2 th
3.	Wind orientation	3.592	0.743	3 th
4.	Humidity	2.974	0.812	4 th

Source: Field Work (2023)

Table 2 shows the problems associated with thermal comfort in the study area which reveals that the major problems are Solar radiation, temperature and clouds with the highest mean score of 4.2123 and ranked as the first followed by Humidity design consideration with the second highest mean score of 3.8045 and ranked as the second. Wind orientation is the third in ranking with mean score of 3.5922. According to Macpherson (1962) amongst the four environmental variables (air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity and radiant temperature), air temperature and humidity are the ones that have more influence on thermal sensation. Earlier research has shown that temperature and humidity have substantial effect on the perception of air quality. These studies (Fang et al., 1998a; Toftum et al., 1998) indicate that the

quality of air perceived in indoor spaces reduces with rise in indoor humidity and/or temperature. Wang, et al., (2009) and Giannopoulou et al. (2014) in their study used air temperature and humidity on human thermal comfort as thermal comfort indices. Ochedi et al. (2016) corroborated the study of Wan et al. (2009) who argued that indoor air temperature and relative humidity seems to be the most significant parameters to determine thermal comfort level. Another study by Toledo et al. (2016) for evaluating the risks of overheating in new buildings in United Kingdom concentrated on two environmental parameters, indoor air temperature and relative humidity. These studies give the idea of the importance of air temperature and humidity on human thermal comfort. This does not imply that other climatic variables do not have an effect on thermal comfort in buildings.

What are promising ways to improve thermal comfort in and around the building’s environment?

Table 3: Possible and promising ways to improve thermal comfort

S/N	Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Rank
1	By minimizing conductive heat flow	4.222	1.584	1 st
2	By minimizing infiltration	4.161	1.895	2 nd
3	By minimising solar gain	3.904	0.876	3 rd
4	By promoting ventilation	3.696	0.883	4 th
5	By promoting radiant cooling	2.921	0.774	5 th
6	By providing evaporative cooling	2.509	0.893	6 th
7	By providing conductive cooling	1.906	0.833	7 th

Source: Field Work (2023)

Table 3 shows the possible and promising ways to improve thermal comfort in and around the building’s environment which reveals that the possible and promising ways are by minimizing conductive heat flow with mean score of 4.2223 and ranked as the first followed by minimizing infiltration with mean score of 4.1612 is ranked as the second. By minimizing solar gain with mean score of 3.9043, and promoting ventilation with mean score of 3.6965 respectively.

Survey results in Table 4 considered basically the sizes of windows but not types. Studies have already established the effectiveness of different window types, wall to window ratio as regards day lighting and thermal comfort. From the T test analysis respondents affirm that larger window

sizes using appropriate glass types and thickness is statistically significant in achieving thermal comfort in studio spaces. Other factors of openings like luminous level, distance of light to individual task will be considered in building simulation survey. Other barriers like burglar proofs that also reduce the daylight into spaces as generally observed hence the choice of larger window openings as recorded in the survey. It is of worth to note that Table 4 indicate 100% of respondents agree that high level windows are better openable instead of fixed, conversely most high level fenestrations in the buildings observed are fixed. 80 % of the respondent agree that fixed window glazing at certain positions/heights on the building affect their lighting and comfort.

Table 4: Building Components

		Highly Insignificant	Insignificant	Slightly Significant	Significant	Highly Significant	Mean	Remark
How do you think these sizes of window openings in lecture spaces affect your lighting and comfort?	900mm X 900mm	17	4	11	0	0	1.81	I
	1200mm X 1200mm	2	12	10	8	3	2.94	I
	1500mm X 1500mm	0	0	14	18	6	3.79	S
	1800mm x 1200mm	0	0	6	9	22	4.43	S
	Others	0	0	4	3	2	3.78	S

Source: Field Work (2023)

Key: 1.00 – 3.00 = Insignificant (I)

3.01 – 5.00 = Significant (S)

The wind experienced at any given location is highly dependent on local topography and other factors, and instantaneous wind speed and direction vary more widely than hourly averages. The average hourly wind speed in Bauchi experiences **significant** seasonal variation over the course of the year. The **windier** part of the year

lasts for **6 months**, from **November** to **May**, with average wind speeds of more than **7.1 miles per hour**. The **windiest** days of the year is the end of **January** with an average hourly wind speed of **9.2 miles per hour**. The **calmer** time of year lasts for five and half months, from **Mid-May** to **November**.

Figure 8: Average Annual Mean Wind Speed for Bauchi, Nigeria
Source: Weatherspark.com

The amount of heat exchange between humans in a space and the air around them increases with air velocity. In some situations, a higher air velocity may be preferable. For instance, in hot weather, a fan might be switched on to speed up how quickly the body can lose heat to the environment. Survey result indicate that there is insufficient wind speed all through the year especially periods from April to October making the studio very uncomfortable without mechanical ventilation.

5. Conclusion

The research came to the conclusion that the major comfort and natural ventilation are human comfort and natural ventilation, natural ventilation for indoor air quality, natural ventilation for passive cooling, and natural ventilation for cooling after going through such evaluation process and becoming familiar with the effects of thermal comfort on natural ventilation in institutional buildings. The problems associated with thermal comfort in the study area are solar radiation, temperature and clouds, humidity design consideration, and wind orientation. The possible and promising ways to improve thermal comfort in and around the building's environment are by minimizing conductive heat flow, by minimizing infiltration, by minimizing solar gain and by promoting ventilation.

Recommendations

With respect to the observations derived from this study, the research has provided some important recommendations for policy makers and practitioners as follows:

1. Building developers should not consider cost alone as the focus of building developments. Attention and consideration should be given to thermal comfort, energy demand, energy

consumption and the effects of building development on the environment.

2. There is need for high-level window openings to generate ventilation by both wind and stack effect.
3. The results of the analysis of case studies have confirmed thermal discomfort in buildings, the need to improve comfort level in Higher Educational buildings and reduce energy demand due to too much reliance on mechanical cooling systems.
4. Design should focus on approach, techniques and processes that will improve efficiency of energy in buildings without disregarding user comfort.
5. Shading devices should be provided for openings exposed to direct solar radiation.

6. Reference

- Abiodun, O.E (2014): Thermal Comfort and Occupant Behaviour in a Naturally Ventilated Hostel in Warm-Humid Climate of Ile-Ife, Nigeria: Field Study Report During Hot Season. *Global Journal of HUMAN-SOCIAL SCIENCE: B Geography, Geo-Sciences, Environmental Disaster Management* 14 (4) 1.0.
- Arif, M., Katafygiotou, M., Mazroei, A., Kaushik, A., & Elsarrag, E. (2016). Impact of indoor environmental quality on occupant well-being and comfort: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Sustainable Built Environment*, 5(1), 1-11.
- Al Horr, Y., Arif, M., Katafygiotou, M., Mazroei, A., Kaushik, A., & Elsarrag, E. (2016). "Impact of indoor environmental quality on occupant well-being and comfort: A review of the literature." *International*

- Journal of Sustainable Built Environment*, 5 (1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbsbe.2016.03.006>
- Amasuomo, T. T., & Amasuomo, J. O. (2016). Perceived thermal discomfort and stress behaviours affecting students' learning in lecture theatres in the humid tropics. *Buildings*, 6(2), 18.
- Mora, R., & Bean, R. (2018). Thermal comfort: Designing for people. *ASHRAE J*, 60(2), 40-46.
- ASHRAE Standard 55-2004. Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy, Atlanta: American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-conditioning Engineers. Inc., USA, 2004
- Beccali, M., Strazzeri, V., Germanà, M. L., Melluso, V., & Galatioto, A. (2018). Vernacular and bioclimatic architecture and indoor thermal comfort implications in hot-humid climates: An overview. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, 1726–1736.
- Bello, M.M, Allu-Kangkum, E.L.A, Nimlyat, P.S (2021). Energy Efficiency Assessment of Higher Education Buildings in Bauchi, Nigeria. *Journal of Contemporary Research in the Built Environment ISSN: 2636-4468*, 5 (1 & 2), 2021. Department of Building, University of Uyo.
- Charles C. M., (2020). Thermal Comfort Assessment of Primary School Children in a Warm and Humid Climate, A case study of Imo State, Nigeria, school of Science, Engineering and Environment conference, University of Salford.
- Fanger, P. O. (1970). Thermal comfort. Analysis and applications in environmental engineering. Thermal comfort. Analysis and applications in environmental engineering.
- Harvey, L. D. (2009). Reducing energy use in the buildings sector: measures, costs, and examples. *Energy Efficiency*, 2(2), 139-163.
- Huang, P., Kumar, P., Giannopoulou, G., & Thiele, L. (2014, October). Energy efficient Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling scheduling for mixed-criticality systems. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Embedded Software* (pp. 1-10).
- Jay, O., Capon, A., Berry, P., Broderick, C., de Dear, R., Havenith, G., ... & Ebi, K. L. (2021). Reducing the health effects of hot weather and heat extremes: from personal cooling strategies to green cities. *The Lancet*, 398(10301), 709-724.
- Kama, H.G. (2023). Assessment of the Relationship between Cerebrospinal Meningitis outbreaks and Climatic Elements in Jos North Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria. 8 (4.)34-45.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Lança, M., Coelho, P. J., & Viegas, J. (2019). Enhancement of heat transfer in office buildings during night cooling— reduced scale experimentation. *Building and Environment*, 148, 653–667.
- Muhammad U. K., (2021). Assessment of Passive Cooling Potentials to Enhance Thermal Comfort in Office Buildings in Dry Sub-Humid Climate. IOP Conf. Ser.: *Material Science Engineering 1107 012174*.
- Munonye, C.C. & Ji, Y., (2018). Rating the components of Indoor Environmental Quality in Nigeria. Paper presented at the Engineering conference, University of Uyo
- Ochedi, E.T., & Taki, A. H. (2016). Low Cost Approach to Energy Efficient Buildings in Nigeria: A Review of Passive Design Options. *21st Century Human Habitat: Issues, Sustainability and Development Proceedings of the Joint International Conference (Jic) Akure*, 47–55.
- Olanipekun, E. A., Olugboyega, O., & Ojelabi, R. A. (2017). Thermal Comfort and Occupant Behaviour in Naturally Ventilated Students' Hostel Buildings: A Case of Covenant University. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 9(7), 44–60.
- Sharaidin, K., Burry, J., & Salim, F. (2012). Integration of digital simulation tools with parametric designs to evaluate kinetic façades for daylight performance. *ECAADe 30 - Digital Physicality*, 2, 691–

700. https://cpb-us-e1.wpmucdn.com/blogs.uoregon.edu/dist/9/447/files/2015/06/Sharaidin_ecaade2012_kineticfacades_ltg-oeomx3.pdf
- Tammy A. T. & Oweikeye A. J. (2016). Perceived Thermal Discomfort and Stress Behaviours Affecting Students' Learning in Lecture Theatres in the Humid Tropics. *Buildings* (2075-5309), 6(2).
- Toftum, J., Jørgensen, A. S., & Fanger, P. O. (1998). Upper limits of air humidity for preventing warm respiratory discomfort. *Energy and Buildings*, 28(1), 15-23.
- Toledo, L., Cropper, P. C., & Wright, A. J. (2016). *Unintended consequences of sustainable architecture : Evaluating overheating risks in new dwellings.* c, 7. <http://www.plea2016.org/index.html>
- Wang, S., Yan, C., & Xiao, F. (2012). Quantitative energy performance assessment methods for existing buildings. *Energy and Buildings*, 55, 873–888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.08.037>
- Waziri, N. & Usman, A. & Enaburekhan, J. (2015). Optimum temperature and solar radiation periods for Kano using flat plate collector. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*. 13. 570-578. 10.1108/JEDT-01-2013-0006.